

**A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON EFFICACY OF DOWRY
PROHIBITION ACT, 1961 WITH THE “BILL FOR PREVENTION OF
EXTRAVAGANZA AND UNLIMITED EXPENDITURE ON
MARRIAGES IN KERALA, 2021**

by

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ABSTRACT

Dowry, also called as Kanyadaan in Indian Hindu marriage, It is the amount paid in currency or any materialistic things by the bride's family to the bridegroom's family members, as well as the bride's voluntarily tied knot with the bridegroom. Kanyadanam has been consider as an important aspect of Hindu marriage rituals. Our culture is deeply steeped in the social menace of dowry. Dowry-related offenses, such as dowry-related deaths, dowry-related murder, dowry-related suicides, and dowry-related demand, are horrifying crimes committed against women. Women in all communities are the communicators of their ancestors' former civilizations and backgrounds. As from womb until the grave, women are obliged to pay a high price for their maturation, with just a few exceptions. Women's inequality begins when they are born. We consider women as God's ultimate gift to mankind but we somewhere fail to prove it. Surprisingly, our Indian constitution programs remains unsuccessful since the socio-cultural provision for the frequent exercise of dowry practices have remained untouched, and hence the practise of giving and receiving dowry continues. Currently in India, we are continuing the pattern of giving and receiving dowry in many case laws.

The Apex court was asked to instruct the High court and district courts for statutory interpretation of law on the topic in light of the existing legislation to combat the "social menace of bride burning and dowry demand," while also being watchful of ongoing efforts to

enlist the help of the alleged husband's family members, even if they played no significant interest in the crime and even if they live in distant locations.

This paper primarily focuses on the causes for failure of dowry Prohibition Act in our country, so that a new bill passed in Kerela with certain new provisions which will be best suited for current dowry harassment issues in our country. It also aims on focusing general laws in IPC related to dowry with few case laws. It examines the need when and how this act came into force. Lastly the researcher will conclude by enlighten some key suggestion to combat with the dowry related issues in our country.

Keywords – *Dowry, Effectiveness, Laws, Crime, Social menace.*

INTRODUCTION :

In ancient India, particularly during the Vedic and Indus Civilizations, women were accorded incredible Divine reverence and honoured as goddesses in community, where she performed her unbiased position and was given increased significance in decision-making within societal structures. Even via the use of the great classics, we can see that women's positions were not only equal to men's, but were also influential. In terms of politics, women were on an equal footing with males. Both men and women are equivalent, and both play vital roles in the growth of their families in particular, as well as society in general. But women were given a lower position in Manushastra.¹ Later on, her situation deteriorated to the point where she was robbed of cultural, economical, and political autonomy, making her dependent on the male members within her own family.

In India, dowry has been considered as a useful tool. Marriages are sometimes referred to as the "economic item of the ceremony." The tradition of providing dowry has become increasingly commonplace amongst people from all over the world. A lady is given all of the necessary household items to start her own family. Since the Vedic period, the usage of dowry has been common in India. Women's property- stridhan was recognised in the Classical era as presents from parents, brothers, and relatives. Initially, it was intended to provide additional stability to newlywed couples as they began their marital lives. It also represented a chance for women to accomplish great legacy. Its face has been warped over time, but its ugliest face

¹ Milan Khatri & Dr.Laxman Singh Rawat, A Critical Analysis of Dowry Prohibition Act 1961 And its Efficacy, International Journals of Research And Analytical Review, (Vol 6, Issue 1 March 2019),(Nov 24, 2021, 6 : 43 PM) http://ijrar.com/upload_issue/ijrar_issue_20543163.pdf .

emerges in today's culture, when fathers and mothers spend their entire lives in indebtedness in order to pay dowry in their daughters' wedding, which leads to accidental deaths among the daughters.

"Dowry" implies any wealth or valued security provided or promised to be given, either implicitly or explicitly, according to section 2 of the Dowry Prohibition Act 1961. The Dowry Prohibition Act of 1961, which made the practice of giving or accepting dowry illegal, states that anybody who accepts dowry must remain in custody for five years in prison. The "dowry prohibition officers" were established by Section 8B of the Act. The statute provides that "the State Government can designate as many Dowry Prohibition Officers as it sees suitable and identify the districts in which they shall regulate their authorities and duties under this Act." The Act states that a dowry prohibition officer's job is to "prevent, as far as reasonable, the taking or actively supporting the taking of, or the seeking of, dowry."² This official shall also "gather such proof or information as may be required for the punishment of people" who acquire and encourage others to accept, or seek dowry, according to the law. The Dowry Prohibition Act of 1961 was a partial attempt to regulate the action against dowry system that failed due to little popular support. It uses a fairly broad definition of the term "dowry" and only imposes minor penalties for infractions. The dowry will be for the welfare of the woman or her heirs, according to Section 6; the laws oblige the bride and groom to keep a record of presents.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM: This paper aims to compare the dowry prohibition Act, 1961 and the new bill passed by Kerala, State women Commission. It analyse the lacuna in the prevailing act for our dynamic Indian society. It also provide the ambit where dowry has been seen as an offence.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES :

- To analyse the inefficiency of Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961.
- To study the causes behind transforming nature of dowry from gift to an offense.
- To study the increasing rate of dowry harassment cases in India.

² Supra note 1 at 5.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS :

- Do we need amendment in Dowry Prohibition Act ?
- Whether the amendments in 1983 and 1984 related to dowry under IPC as well Dowry Prohibition Act was successful or not ?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS : Initially Dowry was given as a gift from bride parents or relatives to support the newly wedded couple in establishing their new life however, in 21st century the concept of dowry become a greed and matter of so called prestige.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY : The researcher has taken doctrinal method of research which includes some articles and journals as a sources for this research .

Primary Sources – Legislations.

Secondary Sources – Articles and Journals.

METHOD OF CITATION : The method of citation followed in this research paper is the Harvard bluebook method of citation, 20th edition.

SCOPE OF STUDY : The researcher has limited the scope of research to Indian laws and its comparison with the different era of Indian society only.

LITERATURE REVIEW :

1. Dr. Mridul Eapen & Adv J Sandhaya, Dowry Prohibition Act : Not too beneficial in its current form, deshabhmani article.

The author here essentially focus on the provisions of Dowry prohibition Act 1961. He describe about the efficacy of provisions in current situation. In his suggestion he describe about what

could be the measures can be taken to combat with the social evil of dowry which is the present need of the hour.

2. Dowry: Women's panel submits draft Bill to govt., The Hindu.

The author has discussed about the new bill proposed by Kerala state women Commission in relation to amend the certain legislation of the prevailing act and also recommended to bring new laws while viewing the today's situation of our country. In that the author also talked about the online campaign where the families were asked to share their opinion about Dowry Prohibition Act and also to take pledge against dowry.

3. Muhammed Sabith, After Multiple Young Women Die in Kerala, Discussion on Dowry, Women's Rights Gain Traction, The Wire.

Here the author mainly limit their words in respect to dowry prohibition Act in Kerala because number of tragic death occurred due to dowry in Kerala. So the group of social activist came forward for change in social attitudes and government mechanism. He also highlighted that the state doesn't have Dowry Prohibition Officer. So there were lot of domestic violence cases were raised with an issue relating to dowry.

4. Milan Khatri & Dr.Laxman Singh Rawat, A Critical Analysis of Dowry Prohibition Act 1961 And its Efficacy, International Journals of Research And Analytical Review, (Vol 6, Issue 1 March 2019).

Author basically put forth the concept of dowry in detail and the essentials elements related to it. He also tries to describe about the kind of similar offense related to women such as Sati Prevention Act 1987, cruelty in marriages and some general laws of IPC dealing with dowry. He also focus upon the concept of dowry according to Hindu Law in his introduction and conclusion. At the end paper provide few suggestions enlightening the changing concept of dowry from a gift to an offence with the changing time.

5. Vageshwari Deswal, Dowry Prohibition Act- Attempting legal solution to a social problem, The Times of India.

The author here, summarized the legal solution of dowry related issues passed by the Supreme Court in different judgements. She also discussed about the case of Rajesh Sharma v. State of UP (2017) where girl tried to rope in all the family member along with the groom into the

dowry crime. After that case only court passes some guidelines in order to check the misuse of the act.

DOWRY PROHIBITION ACT AND ITS INEFFICIENCY: The Indian law regarding dowry are called as the Dowry Prohibition Act was introduced on May 1, 1961, with the goal of prohibiting the offering or accepting of a dowry. Dowry involves properties, goods, or money provided by either party to the marriage, by either party's families, or by some relatives with the marriage, according to the Dowry Prohibition Act. In India, the Dowry Prohibition Act extends to people of all faiths. The Dowry Prohibition Act's initial draught was largely seen as inadequate in preventing the practice of dowry. Furthermore, failing to satisfy dowry expectations was still related to specific types of abuse against women. In the case of *Soni devraj Bhai Babar Devraj Bhai v. State of Gujarat*³, the Supreme Court referenced Pt. Jawahar Lal Nehru's statement to emphasize the importance of law in addressing with dowry as a social evil: "Statute cannot generally give remedy to this crucial social problem by itself." The Supreme Court of India remarked in the foregoing case that the social issue of dowry has been in Indian culture for a long time and remains that way. However, legal consequences such as prohibitions and penalties are several steps toward such flexibility. As a result, the Dowry Prohibition Act of 1961 was enacted to fulfil these objectives. Stridhan defines as whatever a woman can assert as her own property somewhere in a married family in general. Jewellery provided by her family or by the in-laws, presents given to her at the time of her wedding or later, and dowry materials given by her bride's family would also be included. Women's property are typically used to reflect her proportion of her parents' financial gains.

The Punjab and Haryana high court held in the case of *Bhai Sher Jang Singh vs. Smt. Virinder Kaur*⁴ that the groom's side is obligated to return any assets received by the bride's side at the time of marriage, including properties, jewels, cash, and other valuables. The court held that Bhai Sher Jang Singh and his family were accused for committed a criminal betrayal of trust with the jewellery and other stridhan. She had consigned to her husband for safe care and which he had fraudulently utilized under section 406 of the IPC. Punishment for insisting dowry- If any person ask for dowry, directly or indirectly, from the parents or in case any other relatives of a bride or bridegroom, as the case may be, he shall be punished with

³ AIR 1991 SCR (3) 812.

⁴ AIR 1979 Cri. L J 493.

an imprisonment for a minimum term period of six months, but not more than two years, and also with a fine not exceeding ten thousand rupees. Provided, however, that the Law imposes a sentence of less than six months' imprisonment for an appropriate and particular cause to be stated in the court decision. In the case of *Social Action Forum for Manav Adhikar and others v. Union of India Ministry of Law and Justice and others (2018)*⁵, the court established some restrictions to prevent brides from enlisting the help of the groom's entire family in the offense. This weakening of the legislation drew criticism from a number of sectors since the court concentrated on surface statistics rather than delving into the intricacies of the cases.

BILL FOR PREVENTION OF EXTRAVAGANZA AND UNLIMITED EXPENDITURE ON MARRIAGES IN KERALA, 2021 :

Extravagance in pre- and post-wedding rituals in various castes and religious groups would be covered by the Bill, which further proposes a punishment for offenders. The commission had previously started a campaign to raise awareness about extravagant weddings and dowry-related harassment against women in the household. During this time, a media effort with the phrase "End dowry" was held, particularly on social media platforms. Ministers, people's representatives, artists, and sportspeople will all take part in the four-month of internet campaign, which ended on November 26, which is Dowry Prohibition Day in the state. The administration had also received the committee's suggestions on revisions to the Dowry Prohibition Act. It had stated that any gifts given to either party during the marriage or specifically at the time of the marriage are not suppose to considered dowry under Clause 2 of Section 3 of the Act. Furthermore, dowry was covertly shifting hands in the State under the guise of presents. Complaints were not really brought under the Act in such marriages until a woman died.⁶

It was also suggested that a provision must be added to the Dowry Prohibition (Maintenance of Lists of Presents to the Bride and Bridegroom) Rules, 1985, requiring that a list of gifts taken by the bridegroom or his family need to be signed by both the couple and their respective parents or guardians, in presence of a notary, and put forth with an application for recognition of marriage, as well as an affidavit must be given to the dowry prohibition officer by the family of bride keeping with the safety from harassment by the groom side. In recent months, the state

⁵ AIR 2018 SC 4273.

⁶ Dowry: Women's panel submits draft Bill to govt., *The Hindu*, (Nov 26, 2021, 9 : 37 PM) <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/kerala/dowry-womens-panel-submits-draft-bill-to-govt/article35838538.ece> .

has been devastated by a succession of fatalities of young women as a result of dowry harassment.

1ST RESEARCH QUESTION & HYPOTHESIS PROVED :

1. The provision of charging the person who receive dowry under Section 3 of the Act is a key stumbling block to the Act's efficient execution. The modified clause of Sec.7, which states that a confession made by the accused by committing an offense is not criminally liable under this Act, should be highly published in order for more individuals to come forward with dowry-related accusations. The sender of the dowry is usually under duress from the other side as well as the demands of social conventions; an empathic attitude to the giver is required. The provider should be seen as a victim rather than an offender, and his or her penalty should be eliminated or reduced.

2. Section 6 of the Act⁷, which specifies that dowries that has been obtained by anyone other than the bride-to-be must be relocated to her within three months, depending on whether they were given before, during, or after the wedding, or the recipient will be punished, should be investigated by the prohibition officers. For that matter it is important to have fair examination which is rarely done by the officers. So here we can say that reckless behaviour of officers are one of the cause for inefficiency of the Act.

3. Despite efforts to strengthen the legislation by embedding or discarding certain sections/subsections, most notably the 1984 and 1986 amendments, dowry continues to rise unchecked. As previously stated, the majority of cases recorded under the Act in the state is very low, despite the fact that there are significantly more fatalities recorded as a result of dowry. One important reason for the Act's inefficiency is to control the threat is that the provider is supposed to file a complaint.

4. While the Dowry Prohibition Act is a Central Act, this may be possible for our state assembly to make suitable state changes, as Bihar and Himachal Pradesh have undertaken. Keeping in mind the concerns that arose throughout the Act's review and application.

⁷ Dr. Mridul Eapen & Adv J Sandhaya, Dowry Prohibition Act : Not too beneficial in its current form, deshabhmani ,(Nov 26, 2021, 12 : 07 PM) <https://www.deshabhmani.com/english/articles/dowry-prohibition-act/4536> .

2nd RESEARCH QUESTION PROVED : In marital cases, Section 498A is perhaps the most often cited statute. The fact that it is admissible as evidence, non-bailable, as well as the low conviction rate, expresses concern about abuse of the legislation. There appears to be a significant difference between the number of cases filed and those that end in a verdict. This creates severe doubt on the credibility of such charges. However, the increasing percentage of mortality in such instances is the cause for the low number of crimes. The majority of these cases are resolved, so the women either do not appear or become antagonistic. In *Arnesh Kumar v. State of Bihar (2014)*⁸, the Court decided that prosecutions of a person should not be happen randomly at anytime , and that arrests for offences under Section 498A IPC should only be made in extraordinary situation , and only after documenting reasonable grounds by composing in compliance with Section 41(1)(b) of the CrPC.

SUGGESTIONS :

1. The first step must be a social boycott and public humiliation of those who offer and receive dowry. We should refrain from engaging in any wedding that promotes dowry.
2. Educating and enabling girls to speak up for themselves and their parents is the most vital step in the right path. One must invest in their children's education in try to inculcate self-reliance and independence in them.
3. It would be preferable for the judiciary to provide regulations for wedding spending control, alter and update them as needed, and guarantee their proper execution.
4. When it comes to the application of anti-dowry legislation, it's generally said that anti-dowry legislation is noticed more in violation than in compliance. However, because dowry is a socio-legal concern, it cannot be addressed just by legislation unless members of society step forward and effectively cooperate with law-enforcement agencies to combat this scourge.
5. There is also a need to establish social view and actuate public opinion against dowry through the help of comprehensive educational incentives at all levels, primarily among the rural people.

⁸ AIR 2014 SC (8) 273.

6. Grassroots initiatives, such as those at the elementary level, must be organised with the participation of local organizations. Initiatives taken by some local authorities such as Panancheri and Nilambur panchayats to combat the social evil may be substantiated and emulated if found to be effective.

CONCLUSION : Dowry is usually regarded as more important than the woman herself. Her conjugal power, which looked to be the exclusive depends upon marriage, is given a basic concept. She is increasingly being seen as a useful instrument for amassing ordinary money and fortunes. During the last decade or two, our country has experienced the dark afflictions of the dowry failing system in a bigger harsh form in substantially all sections of the country due to the fact it's far performed by nearly all groups within the community. It is nearly a regular occurrence that not only betrothed females are abused, ridiculed, pushed to commit suicide, leave spouses, and so on, tormented and sickly treated, but many are even burned to death because their parents are unable to meet the dowry requirements of in-laws or their husbands. It cannot be ignored that the Act will only function if the institutionalized gender expectations and practices that emerge to legalize this tradition of giving dowry are changed, such as making it more viable to bind the parties into marriages with desirable families and stigmatized girls who return to their own family due to dowry harassment. Marriage should not be seen as removing a bride's relationships to her natal home/family, to which she should have an everlasting and undisputed claim, as defined by her parents. Women must be financially empowered, and attitudes must shift.

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4. Vageshwari Deswal, Dowry Prohibition Act- Attempting legal solution to a social problem, The Times of India.
5. Interpret law to curb menace; be cautious: SC to courts on dowry death cases, The Indian Express.
6. M.P Praveen, Many women unaware of dowry law, finds survey, The Hindu.

Abbreviations :

1. IPC – Indian Penal Code
2. SC – Supreme Court.

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